

FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN STUDENTS

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Annotation. *This article studies the formation of professional competence determined by the effectiveness of the implementation of skills and abilities in the process of professional activity of a specialist in accordance with the requirements of professional qualifications. The acquisition of knowledge and skills in a competency involves the rejection of the traditional approach and, in addition, specific knowledge, skills and abilities.*

Key words: *education, process, professional competence, skills, formation, approach, component.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуется формирование профессиональной компетентности, определяемой эффективностью реализации умений и навыков в процессе профессиональной деятельности специалиста в соответствии с требованиями профессиональной квалификации. Приобретение знаний и умений по компетенции предполагает отказ от традиционного подхода и, кроме того, от специфических знаний, умений и навыков.*

Ключевые слова: *образование, процесс, профессиональная компетентность, навыки, формирование, подход, компонент.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola kasbiy malaka talablariga muvofiq mutaxassisning kasbiy faoliyati jarayonida ko'nikma va ko'nikmalarni amalga oshirish samaradorligi bilan belgilanadigan kasbiy kompetentsiyani shakllantirishini o'rganadi. Kompetentsiyada bilim va ko'nikmalarni egallash an'anaviy yondashuvni va qo'shimcha ravishda aniq bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni rad etishni o'z ichiga oladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *ta'lim, jarayon, kasbiy kompetentsiya, malaka, shakllanish, yondashuv, component.*

The educational process at a university has clear goals related to the formation of professional competence in future specialists. According to L.O.Filatova, the concept of competence includes not only cognitive and operational-technological components, but also motivational, ethical, social and behavioral. Competence also means the ability to mobilize acquired knowledge, skills, experience and methods of behavior in a specific situation, specific activity. From this definition follows the need to form and evaluate the level of formation of the personal qualities of the future specialist and methods of activity in a specific professional situation.

The categorical apparatus of the study of theoretical foundations and practical aspects of the formation of professional competence of future specialists in the process of their training in higher educational institutions is analyzed. It was noted that readiness for professional activity combines awareness of the role and social responsibility, the desire to actively perform professional tasks, the attitude to actualization and mobilization of the relevant qualities, knowledge and skills acquired in a higher educational institution. After all, readiness is a natural result of a broadly professional orientation, which implies professional education, upbringing, self-education and professional self-determination. It is substantiated that the main characteristic of

professional competence is taking into account psychological, social and cultural factors that depend on the individual's social affiliation and the specific situation. The modern concepts, essence, and content of the competence approach in education have been studied. It was revealed that the basis of qualification requirements should be the components of professional competence, which are related to the realization of the goal of education at different levels, taking into account modern socio-psychological requirements and real conditions of education.

Competent organization of training and subsequent assessment of the quality of preparation, for example, for teaching activities stimulates the targeted, continuous development of the competence of future teachers, their methodological culture, personal professional growth, and their use of modern pedagogical technologies. In general, this ensures an increase in the efficiency and quality of teaching work, and also allows us to identify prospects for using the potential capabilities of teachers.

The structural components of professional training of higher school students are characterized and it is proved that the teacher must be able to model the educational process in accordance with the modern requirements of science and practice. The essence, content and functions of the professional competence of future specialists are defined and substantiated. The effectiveness of the training of specialists in higher education institutions based on the competence approach in order to ensure the formation of a highly qualified specialist has been proven.

Formulation of the problem. Updating the content of education, focusing on a new type of pedagogical worldview that meets the socio-cultural challenges of the era, prioritizing the formation of key competences in the intellectual, civic-legal, communication, and information spheres in student youth - these and other features should certainly be reflected in professional and personal qualities future specialists. Higher educational institutions of the third millennium are obliged to train a competent specialist who possesses integral, systematic knowledge, is a person of culture, a leader of the ideas of state building and democratic changes.

It should be noted that psychological and pedagogical studies in the field of professional training of students testify to different approaches of scientists regarding the interpretation of the category «professional competence». Researchers study it both as a characteristic of a person, and as the implementation of functions, and as a set of communicative, constructive, organizational skills of a person.

In our opinion, the defining principles, based on which it is possible to increase the effectiveness of developing the professional competence of a future specialist, are:

- the principle of systematic organization of information and cognitive actions;
- the principle of partnership between teacher - student, student - student;
- the principle of initiative in identifying problems, structuring them and finding solutions.

The implementation of a systematic approach actualizes the focus of the educational process at a university on developing students' cultural foundations and the comprehensive development of general and professional abilities. It is important to develop basic competencies that determine the success of solving the main functional tasks of professional activity. This is competence in the field of personal qualities; competence in goal setting; competence in motivating others and self-motivation; competence in developing an activity program and making management decisions; competence in the field of information basis of activities; competence in organizing practical activities.

A significant component of the formation of professional competence is knowledge. A rational solution to a problem is based on knowledge of the subject area (concepts, theories,

concepts) and procedural knowledge (description of the sequence of actions in the decision-making process). Domain knowledge will depend on the area of its application, i.e. they are situational. Therefore, the broader a person's horizons, the better he can solve a problem.

At the same time, it must be borne in mind that there is a problem of the functioning of theoretical knowledge in the context of competence, in decision-making activities. Knowledge itself is only a general cognitive basis for understanding a problem and making a decision. Only a sufficiently high quality of acquired knowledge will provide the future specialist with the necessary basis for the formation of competence. And this is not only awareness, consistency, completeness, flexibility of subject knowledge, but also knowledge about procedures for analyzing situations, procedures for identifying problems, procedures for decision-making (knowledge of how to act in a decision-making situation). Value-semantic knowledge is also important, answering the question of what decision to make and why this particular decision.

In addition, competence is considered through the system of levels of professional skill. Also, according to scientists, competence occupies a transitional state between diligence and perfection. It is considered as awareness, authority [2, p.7; 13, p. 34; 14, p. 82]. As we can see, scientists distinguish not narrow knowledge of the subject, but mastery of experience based on philosophy, psychology, anatomy, etc., that is, on deep comprehensive knowledge of theory. That is why the ability not only to interest in information, but also the ability to conduct a dialogue, exchange ideas with listeners becomes an indicator of professional competence. Therefore, the involvement of students in scientific and research work, in the development of their scientific spirit is also a necessary indicator of competence.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The problem of professional training has always been relevant in domestic pedagogy and psychology. A significant contribution to the development of its various aspects was made by research on the study of the structure of professional activity: M. Dyachenko, V. Zagvyazynskyi, L. Kandybovich, N. Kuzmina, V. Slastyonin, V. Shadrikov, etc., on the intensification and optimization of the educational process in higher education school: S. Arkhangel'skiy, A. Verbitskiy, E. Zeyer, V. Savinykh, A. Usova, etc., on modeling students' cognitive activity: V. Bepalko, Yu. Kulyutkin, V. Lyaudis, N. Talizina, etc. At the same time, the construction of professional education based on the competence approach and its use in assessing the quality of training of future specialists led to the appearance of a large number of works devoted to the study of professional competence and the search for optimal conditions for effective methods of its formation, namely: V. Adolf, Yu. Vardanyan A. Kochnev and others.

Obviously, knowledge can fulfill its functions if it is supported by appropriate skills, a vision of the situation as a whole, as well as connections between individual elements of the system.

Finally, the main core of competence is a set of specific skills that ensure the adoption of optimal decisions aimed at further productive development of the system.

We include among such skills, first of all, the ability to detect and comprehend the analyzed system (identify it). This may involve tracing the historical roots and identifying the development of the problem over time, which allows it to be comprehensively investigated. This may be the procedure for posing a problem, its awareness and designation, which is the key point of the entire process. The basis of the skill and, at the same time, its manifestation is the verbalization of the essence of the problem, its articulation. The ability to see and articulate a problem in a multifaceted way, to change and expand the very formulation of the question allows one to realize that the

situation is not as simple and linear as it seemed at first. Deployment and explication (interpretation, explanation) of various, primarily hidden and non-obvious aspects of the situation associated with different scenarios, makes it possible to determine the risks and prices that will have to be paid for certain choices made in a given situation. You can find a seemingly brilliant solution to a problem, but if the problem itself is incorrectly formulated, then the effect of implementing this solution will be zero at best.

An important skill is the analysis of a problem situation, when difficulties determined by the context of a specific problem are highlighted, and factors influencing decision-making are identified. As the practice of teaching students has shown, mental maps (mind maps) are an effective tool for analyzing a problem situation.

A clear sequence of actions leading to decision-making and its prognostic assessment eliminated the inconsistency, inconsistency and associated errors inherent in students, and did not allow unreasonable decision-making, which was an indicator of the development of professional competence.

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